

ADVERTISING TEXT IS A COMMUNICATIVE UNIT WITH A SPECIAL
STRUCTURAL AND SEMANTIC FEATURES

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Introduction. *The world of modern man in the era of the development of audiovisual and electronic media is a media space, which is nothing more than a specific environment where the virtual life of the whole society, as well as individual social groups and individuals, takes place. The media space, in turn, generates a media fact - “an informational error or a deliberately false message modeled as reliable”, as well as a media text that replaces the traditional journalistic work. It manifests itself as a fragment of media discourse and is completely determined by it.*

“The coherence and integrity of the traditional text began to recede into the background. Verbally or virtually designed fragments, pieces of reality began to enjoy popularity.

The term «advertising» comes from the Latin «reklamare», which means to respond, object, express displeasure. Advertising in English is denoted by the term «advertising», which in English means notification and is interpreted as drawing the consumer's attention to a product (good, service) and disseminating advice, appeals, suggestions, recommendations to purchase this product or service. Advertising books give a large number of different definitions of advertising:

“Advertising - familiarizing the consumer with a product or service offered by a given manufacturing, commercial or other enterprise.” “Advertising is a paid, unidirectional and non-personal appeal carried out through the media and other

types of communication, campaigning in favor of any product or service.”

“Advertising - non-personal forms of communication carried out through paid means of disseminating information, indicating the source.”

In addition, advertising is extremely interesting as a special rhetorical phenomenon, since “the object of rhetoric can be any kind of speech communication that is considered from the point of view of a consciously chosen impact on the addressee.”

It should be noted that modern linguistic teachings - cognitive linguistics, linguopragmatics, communication theory, the theory of speech acts - have influenced traditional rhetorical canons. If in classical rhetoric, there are 5 stages of text deployment: invention; disposition; elocution; memorization; pronunciation (performance).

In modern media discourse, both the number and content of these concepts have changed: the disposition is correlated with the communicative-textual approach, with speech acts, and elocution turns from decoration into a means of influencing the addressee in order to change his picture of the world.

Returning to the genre diversity, it should be noted that at present the following types of printed texts are distinguished in advertising discourse: short advertising messages, announcements, leaflets, posters and more complex texts, such as “everyday history”, a detailed appeal, an advertising article.

Working with advertising texts has always implied, and presupposes, a deep knowledge of the laws of communication between the buyer and the market. At present, psychophysiological semiotics is dealing with these problems in various countries of the world. In any trading company there are specialists in psycholinguistics and neurophysiology.

Taking into account the criteria and limitations of psychophysiological semiotics in advertising activities, and primarily when working on the source text or already with the finished product, will allow you to carry out all the preparatory work on advertising in the shortest possible time, or, as they say, “without words

and without torment.”

If advertising first attracts the reader or listener with its emotional side, then it should interest him with its content, cause one or another reaction - stimulate a certain emotional state. For example, to please, intrigue, surprise, cheer. Good advertising quickly evokes in the mind of the addressee an idea of the subject - an image and associations associated with it. It forms an advertising image.

The effectiveness of the advertising text is enhanced by the logical selection of the main, most important part of it. Moreover, if the text is short, of five or six words, then only one stressed word is usually distinguished in it, which is placed in the first and last place in the sentence. In an extensive text, such a selection is no longer enough - additional means of influence are needed, for example: opposition, explanation, various linguistic figurative and expressive elements, etc. At the same time, we must not forget that saving language means is an indispensable condition for effective advertising.

Interrogative forms are used in indirect speech tactics as a means of lateral presentation of information. Information is deposited in the subconscious without causing objections from the client. To attract attention, interrogative sentences are used even in headings. Often the question sounds rhetorical and is a pathetic expressive statement, for example:

First wrinkles? Smooth out. Rejuvenate. (advertisement of a cream);

How to give your skin youth for a long time? (advertisement of cosmetics).

How to protect your body? (advertising for medical nutrition)

Conclusion. The conducted research allows us to say that the main thing in the advertising text is the formation of an advertising image with the help of various lexical-syntactic and visual means.

The advertising image creates specific ideas about the subject and evokes certain feelings that influence the behavior of the reader in the right direction. And since the advertising image is formed taking into account the individual characteristics of the advertised object and the common features inherent in a group

of objects, the main features of advertising are a certain organization of linguistic material that reveals the specificity of this sphere of communication, the target orientation of the means of language used and the specific nature of the communication situation, determined by a combination of extralinguistic and linguistic conditions.

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